

Popular Article

Anemia In Dogs and Its Management with Oral and Transfusion Therapy

Sree Krishna Sai, N. Devadevi, A. Abiramy@Prabavathy, K. Rajkumar and P.Vijayalakshmi .

¹MVSc Scholar, Department of Veterinary Medicine ²Assistant Professor, Department of Veterinary Medicine ³Professor, Department of Veterinary Medicine ⁴Professor and Head, Department of Veterinary Clinical Complex ⁵Professor and Head, Department of Veterinary Medicine, Department of Veterinary Medicine, Veterinary Clinical Complex, Rajiv Gandhi Institute of Veterinary Education and Research, Puducherry

Abstract

The aim of the manuscript is to describe about the anemia detection in puppies and adult dogs, their basic and emergency treatment and preventive measures with special reference to tick borne diseases, parasitic infections and other hemorrhagic diseases.

Introduction

Anemia is defined as decrease in hemoglobin or packed cell volume (Giger, 2017). It is generally a symptom of underlying disease and occurs when your dog doesn't produce enough hemoglobin or red blood cells, which carry oxygen to tissues. Energy is then produced by cells and carbon-dioxide is left behind, and then exhaled out of the body through lungs. But with few red blood cells, less oxygen is carried leading to weakness and fatigue.

Causes of anemia

Causes of anemia in dogs is classified as severe blood loss seen in accident or injury and parturition, hidden blood loss seen in ruptured tumor on the spleen, intestinal bleeding (tumor/ulcer), hemorrhagic disorder, parasitic infestations and induced anemia seen in autoimmune diseases, chronic kidney disease, cancer, endocrinal diseases and hepatic diseases. The normal hemoglobin and PCV was 12- 18 g/dl and 35-55% respectively.

Types of anemia

- Blood loss anemia
- Hemolytic anemia
- Aplastic or non-regenerative anemia
- Methemoglobinemia

Signs and symptoms seen in anemia

Based on the underlying disease, the symptoms will vary. It includes:

Common signs noticed were lethargy, decrease appetite, weight loss, exercise intolerance, pale mucous membrane, weakness, labored breathing, swelling in jaw or face, vomiting, black stools, rapid breathing and fast pulse. On palpation splenomegaly, hepatomegaly and lymphadenopathy can be noticed.

Treatment of anaemia

The dogs have hemoglobin between 6 to 12g/dl and PCV between 20 to 35 % is treated with systemic iron sucrose injection and oral hematinics which contain ferrous ascorbate, folic acid, vitamin B12 and minerals like cobalt, copper, iron, manganese and zinc but having hemoglobin less than 6g/dl and PCV < 20% should be recovered with blood transfusion only.

Indications for blood transfusions

Anemic patients should be categorized based on their PCV and types of anemia, whether it is a regenerative or non – regenerative. In regenerative anemia, the reticulocyte count is more than 1% can do better without blood transfusion. Classification of anemia given below based on PCV values and cell morphology and Hb concentration

- Severe anemia - PCV <18%
- Moderate anemia - PCV =18 to 29%
- Mild anemia - PCV =30 to 36%
- Regenerative anaemia - Macrocytic hypochromic blood picture
- Non regenerative anemia - Normocytic normochromic blood picture
- Hemolytic anemia - Neutrophilia with a left shift and monocytosis

Common Indications for blood transfusion

- Blanched mucous membrane
- Blood loss in profuse epistaxis
- Immune mediated hemolytic anemia
- Ecchymosis in hemoprotozoan disease
- Disseminated intravascular coagulopathy (DIC) in sepsis
- Bleeding disorders and Neoplasm
- Surgical blood loss

- Severe thrombocytopenia
- Snake envenomation (Platelet rich plasma)
- Rodenticide toxicity (fresh frozen plasma)
- Acariasis, pediculosis and pulicosis
- Leptospirosis, PVE
- Ancylostomiasis,

Blood Transfusion

Donors selected for blood collection should be young adult lean, good tempered and weigh more than 25 kg for dogs with no history of prior transfusion. It has been regularly vaccinated and dewormed, should be healthy which will be confirmed by history, physical examination and laboratory tests like complete blood count, biochemistry, faecal examination and free of infectious diseases like *Microfilaria*, *Brucella*, *Babesia*, *Ehrlichia*, *Anaplasma PVE*, *CD*, etc. The Hemoglobin and PCV should be >13 g/dl and >40 % respectively in canine donors. Generally, DEA 1.1 –ve are universal donors and suitable for collection.

Blood is collected aseptically from jugular vein over a period of 5 to 10 minutes. Commercial blood bags generally of closed collection system in which blood does not come into contact with environment during collection or separation of blood components, thus chances of bacterial contamination is minimized and allowing for storage of blood products.

Amount of blood to be transfused (ml) = body weight of donor (Kg) x 90 x (desired PCV - recipient PCV) / PCV of donor

Blood components are prepared from whole blood by centrifugation within 8 hours from collection. So, fresh whole blood can be separated into packed red blood cells, platelet-rich plasma or concentrate, fresh frozen plasma and cryoprecipitate. Whole fresh blood transfusion should be transfused within 4 hours of collection

Problems involved in field level blood transfusion

- Lack of blood bags and canine blood donors
- Unavailability of blood typing kits
- No proper knowledge and expertise in transfusion
- No proper storage facilities
- Lack of interest to owners
- Non cooperative donor dogs
- Obese donor dogs in which loose scruff under the neck. So, no proper tracing of jugular vein
- Insufficient amount of blood collected from donor dog due to lack of proper gaining to vein, uncooperative donor dog and lower blood pressure etc
- Development of phlebotomies due to multiple pricks as jugular vein is highly prone for hematomas.

Points to be remember in blood transfusion

- Blood transfusion is not the complete cure. It is a treatment to stabilize the animal, underlying cause should be treated.
- Aim is to deliver immediate oxygen to the tissues.
- Anaemic dog's looks like active and thrombocytopenic dogs are dull.
- Maximum first blood transfusion is safe without checking for blood typing and cross matching but second transfusion onwards animal should be checked every time.
- Common clinical signs of transfusion reactions are fever, vomiting, diarrhoea, shivers and urticarial lesions etc.
- Universal donor dogs (DEA 1.1 negative) owners contact should be maintained because whenever there is in need of emergency can contact them.

Prevention of anemia in dogs

- The dogs should be regularly dewormed
- Dogs should be vaccinated against infectious diseases
- Animals should be free of ectoparasites
- Diet should contain good sources of iron and protein such as egg, mutton spleen, green vegetables, beef liver and chicken.
- In dogs, Vitamin C helps in the absorption of iron from the intestine. The daily requirement of Vit. C in dogs is 500 to 2000 milligrams.

References

- Urs Giger, G.R.Baranidharan. 2017. Clinical approach to anaemia and transfusion practices in dogs and cats
- Abrams-Ogg A. 2000. Practical Blood Transfusion. In: Day M. J. et al. (Eds), BSAVA manual of canine and feline haematology and transfusion medicine, Gloucester, U.K.: British Small Animal Veterinary Association, p. 263–307.